

Synthesis and spectroscopic studies of mixed ligand complexes of cobalt(II) with salicylaldehyde, hydroxyaryl ketones and β -diketones

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Abstract : Reactions of Co^{II} nitrate with two carbonyl compounds (HL and HL') in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratios in ethanol have yielded mixed ligand complexes $[\text{CoLL}'(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ (where HL = salicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxyacetophenone or 2-hydroxypropiophenone and HL' = pentane-2,4-dione, 1-phenylbutane-1,3-dione or 1,3-diphenylpropane-1,3-dione). These complexes have been characterized by elemental analyses, conductances, thermal analyses, magnetic moments, IR, FAB mass, and electronic spectra.

Keywords : Cobalt(II), mixed ligand complexes, ketones.

In the present paper mixed ligand complexes of the type $[\text{CoLL}'(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ (where HL = salicylaldehyde (salH), 2-hydroxyacetophenone (hapH), 2-hydroxypropiophenone (hppH) and HL' = acetylacetone (acacH), benzoylacetone (bzacH) or dibenzoylmethane (dbzmH) are described.

Results and discussion

The reactions of cobalt(II) nitrate with a 1 : 1 molar mixture of two carbonyl compounds (salicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxyacetophenone or 2-hydroxypropiophenone and β -diketones) result in the formation of the mixed ligand complexes (1a-i, Fig. 1). Very low values of molar conductances of Co^{II} complexes (Table 1) indicate their non-electrolytic behaviour¹.

In free salicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxyacetophenone, 2-hydroxypropiophenone, acetylacetone, benzoylacetone and dibenzoylmethane absorption bands due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ have been reported at 1660, 1650, 1640, 1724, 1724 and 1600 cm^{-1} respectively^{2,3}. The mixed ligand complexes of Co^{II} exhibit strong IR absorption bands in the region 1590–1650 cm^{-1} , which may be assigned to coordinated $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ ⁴. The absorption bands at 1453–1563 cm^{-1} may be assigned to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$. Weak absorption bands in the region 400–500 cm^{-1} in the IR spectra of the mixed ligand complexes, which are not present in the free ligands, are attributed to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ vibrations. Similar bands in this region have been assigned to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ vibrations of metal β -diketonates by Nakamoto *et al.*⁵⁻⁷.

The weight loss observed by TGA in the 100–140 °C

Fig. 1. Mixed ligand complexes of cobalt(II).

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the mixed ligand complexes

Compd.	Colour	Decomp. temp. (°C)	Yield (%)	Metal (%) : Found (Calcd.)	Molar conduct. $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	μ_{eff} B.M.
[Co(sal)(acac)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow	145	51	18.49 (18.69)	6	4.27
[Co(sal)(bzac)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Pink	160	47	15.48 (15.66)	4	4.25
[Co(sal)(dbzm)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow	148	42	13.51 (13.41)	10	3.90
[Co(2-hap)(acac)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Brown	260	67	17.79 (17.90)	31	4.12
[Co(2-hap)(bzac)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Brown	250	35	15.10 (15.06)	20	4.90
[Co(2-hap)(dbzm)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow	140	48	12.88 (13.00)	35	4.46
[Co(2-hpp)(acac)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Grey	110	37	17.46 (17.17)	22	3.97
[Co(2-hpp)(bzac)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Brown	210	57	14.32 (14.54)	21	3.92
[Co(2-hpp)(dbzm)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow	138	48	12.47 (12.61)	14	4.33

range for the Co^{II} complexes corresponds to two coordinated water molecules. The complex [Co(sal)(bzac)(H₂O)₂] shows the loss of benzoylacetone moiety at 414 °C giving the species Co(sal) (wt. left 44.4%, calcd. for Co(sal) 47.6%). Thereafter a continuous loss in weight is observed and finally it gets converted to cobalt oxide at 461 °C (wt. left 19.86%, calcd. for CoO 20.10%).

μ_{eff} values (at ~300 K) of Co^{II} complexes (3.90–4.90 B.M.) are slightly higher than spin only value for a d⁷ system due to orbital contribution⁸.

All the complexes exhibit a weak molecular ion peak corresponding to [CoLL']⁺. In addition, peaks due to the corresponding symmetrical complexes CoL₂ and CoL'₂ were also observed as a result of the redistribution reactions :

In all the complexes peaks due to CoL⁺ and CoL'⁺ are also observed due to formation of such species as a result of the loss of one or the other ligand moiety. All the complexes exhibit (M-15)⁺ peaks due to loss of CH₃^{9,10}.

Mixed ligand complexes of Co^{II} exhibit bands at 19512–24271, 16891–18099 and 8547–11210 cm⁻¹, which may be assigned to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3), ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1) transitions respectively^{11–13}. These bands are characteristic of a distorted octahedral geometry.

Experimental

Salicylaldehyde (Merck), 2-hydroxyacetophenone (John Baker), 2-hydroxypropiophenone (Fluka), pentane-2,4-dione (K. light) and ethanol were purified by distillation and 1-phenylbutane-1,3-dione (Sisco Chem) and 1,3-diphenyl-propane-1,3-dione (Sisco Chem) were recrystallized from ethanol before use. Co(NO₃)₂·6H₂O (Fluka)

used was of A.R. grade.

Cobalt was determined volumetrically by EDTA using xylenol orange as indicator¹⁴. Specific conductances were measured at room temperature in DMF using a Systronics direct reading conductivity meter-304. IR spectra were recorded as KBr pellets in the region 400–4000 cm⁻¹ on a Nicolet Magna-550 FTIR spectrophotometer. TGA and DTA studies were carried out on a Rigaku Thermoflex PTC-10A instrument under nitrogen atmosphere. Magnetic measurements were carried out at room temperature (300 K) on a Gouy balance using Hg[Co(NCS)₄] as a calibrant. Electronic spectra were recorded in DMF on a Hitachi U-2000 spectrophotometer. The FAB mass spectra were recorded on a JEOL SX 102/DA-6000 mass spectrometer/data system using argon/xenon (6 kV, 10 mA) as the FAB gas.

Preparation of mixed ligand complexes : To the ethanolic solution of cobalt(II) nitrate (3.43 mmol, 1.03 g in 10 ml ethanol) ethanolic solutions of the two different carbonyl compounds in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratio were added. The contents were stirred for about half an hour at room temperature. The pH of the clear reaction mixture was raised to 6.5 by adding 5% sodium hydroxide solution with constant stirring, which was continued for ~5–6 h, when the complexes precipitated. The precipitates were filtered, washed with ethanol, dried under reduced pressure and analysed.

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Note

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